

Demographic Manifestation of Gender Inequality: A Study of Bhiwani District

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Abstract:- The current study is an attempt to show the gender inequality with reference to demographic manifestation of Bhiwani district from 1991 to 2011. As we all know in demographic manifestation, the sex ratio is an important social indicator that measures the respective status of males and females in a community on how they are treated in terms of equal status and greatly defines the future population composition. Changes in the sex ratio reflect the underlying socio-economic and cultural tendencies in a community. It has an impact on not only the demographic process but also the socioeconomic relationships within the community. The aim of this research is to better understand the spatio-temporal variance in total child sex ratio in India and Haryana. Census of India and Haryana Statistical Abstract data were used to analyze challenges, causes, trends and declining child sex ratios. Bhiwani district one of the districts having low sex ratio in the state. Here our main ethos is get an idea about the district's background in socio-economic profile. Here a tahsils or blocks wise study taken into consideration.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gender refers to the socially constructed characteristics of women and men- such as norms, roles and relationships of and between group of women and men. It varies from society to society and can be changed. Gender equality is a core development objective in its own right. Greater gender equality can enhance productivity, improve development outcomes for next generation and make institutions more representative. Right since the dawn of civilization gender inequality has been a matter of huge debate. In fact, this

debate has taken the shape of enormous social issues. Time and again, certain steps have been taken in order to deal with this monstrous issue related to gender inequality. When we take a glance at history, we see that though the movement related to the abolishment of SATI system, Raja Ram Mohan Roy did try to fill up the gap of inequality and raised his voice in support of women by saying that "They are born not only to devote their life for their male counterparts in marriage and after marriage by burning themselves with the dead body of their husbands. They are as vital for the society as the males are, hence women must not be treated merely as an object of second class society. In fact, they are the ones who are real master of man as well as mankind. If we cannot worship them, then we have no right to burn and hate them." We all know this Sanskrit dictum very well that '*Yatra Naryastu Pujyante, Ramanteh Hee Tatra Devtaa*'. Gender discrimination manifests in many forms in India, right from birth to adulthood. Fewer month of breastfeeding, below par medical care, insufficient nutrition, lack of prenatal, natal and postnatal care result in girls being susceptible to illness, having poor health and shorter life span. Due to the wide prevalence of patriarchal social system, a lot of women are still deprived of the right to own ancestral property, which is mostly given to their non-inclusion in the decision the male child. Several causes are attributed to increasing gender inequality in society. Sex selective abortion, crime against women, domestic violence, different socio-cultural practices, neglect of girl child and son preference are main causes for gender inequality in India.

Pre-natal and post-natal inequalities with females:-

Pre-birth Stage	Female foeticide
Infancy Stage	Female Infanticide and Gender discrimination with particular to (Health, Nutrition and Education)
Childhood Stage	Gender discrimination (health, nutrition, food, education, and other social benefits).
The adolescent stage	Early marriage, rape, discrimination in health care, dress code, use of information technology like mobile phones, their movement are restricted, prostitution, trafficking, eve-teasing etc.
Reproductive stage of women	Domestic violence in the form of sexual (marital rape) psychological, emotionally and physically tortured by intimate partner and his family members).
Old age	In the old age of a women generally faces elderly abuse, (Abused in terms of physical, emotional, psychological and financial abuse).

Here we are concerning with demographic manifestation of gender inequality. Demographic manifestation is one of the best manifestations to show the gender inequality prevailing in the society. In this context, we can discuss about sex ratio (overall and child sex ratio).

Sex ratio is an important social parameter to measure the extent of prevailing equity between males and females in a society at a given point of time. The declining sex ratio leads to gender imbalance which reflects the underlying socio-economic and cultural patterns of a particular society.

In Anthropology and Demography, the decreasing child female to male ratio has been one of important concerns especially for India. According to Nicholas Kristof and Sheryl Wudunn, two Pulitzer Prize winning reporters for the New York Times, ‘violence against women is causing gender imbalances in many developing world, particularly in China, India and Pakistan. Commonly, countries with gender imbalance have these characteristics in common. First is a rapid decline in fertility, either because of preference for smaller families or to comply with their nation’s population control measures. Second, there is pressure for women to give birth to sons, often because of cultural preferences for male heirs. Third, families have widespread access to technology to selectively abort female fetuses. India’s skewed sex ratio figures are indeed unfortunate and alarming. Sadly, while there is much academic discussion on the issue of “India’s Missing Women” there is no tangible change in the mindset of our people. Education has not altered or sensitized society to the rights of women and the dismal of sex ratio in the upper echelons of society. Rising sex ratio at birth (In favor of male child) has been recorded since the early 1980s, which marks the introduction of ultrasound in the field of obstetrics. India is one of the few nations in the world where males outnumber females. According to 2011 census, the sex ratio in India is 940 females per 1000 males. Although there is a marginal improvement from 1991 and 2001 census, where it was 927 and 933, it continues to be significantly adverse towards women. India’s sex ratio of 940 is the lowest amongst the most population countries in the world, namely China (944), Bangladesh (953), Indonesia (1004), Nigeria (1016), Japan (1041), Brazil (1025), USA (1029), Russia (1040).

A. Study Area

The present study is an attempt to examine the spatio-temporal changes in gender inequality and CSR under various socio-cultural realms in Bhiwani district from 1991-2011 by using village level data. A particular emphasis in the study is on the demographic manifestation of gender inequality (Child Sex Ratio). The study endeavors to look into the associated factors. The reasons for gender inequality with particular to CSR in associated areas are not simply measured by biological dimensions only. On the other hand, these need to be examined in terms of various socio-cultural realms of various blocks of Bhiwani district. Despite a commendable progress made on the economic front, it is as the near bottom as regard to gender inequality.

B. Objectives

- To assess the various demographic, socio-cultural, economic and other factors responsible for Gender Inequality and imbalanced SR and CSR in Study Area.
- To know social outlook of society towards female children in study area.
- To analyse the Spatio-temporal trends and pattern of Gender Inequality (SR, CSR) in Bhiwani District.

C. Research Methodology

Research methodology is a vital part of any research work. Research methodology deals with the research method and takes into consideration the logic behind the

methods researcher uses. It depends on the objectives of the research work. In research methodology, the researcher decides what type of tools he/she would be going to use in the study. The present study will be based on data drawn from secondary sources. Census will be the main secondary source of data.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

- **Siddigui and Ahmad** (1971) explained the sex ratios at district level among major religious groups with their rural–urban break-up. The ratio of total population of the district was different from that of either rural or urban population. The population was classified on the basis of religious groups which showed religious composition and the regional variation of sex ratio within its rural and urban components.
- **Krishna and Chandna** (1973) examined the sex composition of Haryana’s population and observed the excessive deficiency of females in the state’s population which was attributable to an unusually low sex ratio at birth and higher rate of mortality, among the females. The difference in the state’s rural and urban sex ratios was considerably smaller than the national average.
- **Banerjee** (1977) studied sex ratio and its correlates in the tribal district of Singhbhum in south Bihar. The sex ratio in the area was strongly influenced by pattern of migration. It was also revealed that the area’s gradually declining sex ratio was attributable to higher female mortality.
- **Chandna and Sidhu** (1979) focused primarily on determinants of sex ratio, sex ratio at birth, male female differentials in mortality and migration besides, factors like wars, famines and status of women also made notable impact on sex ratio. Using village wise census data, they analyzed spatial patterns of sex ratio in south Konkan, Maharashtra during 1951-71.
- **Siddigui** (1982) made a study of regional aspects of sex ratio in U.P. He also worked on same region during 1984. The study based on regional pattern of sex composition of the population of U.P. revealed that socio-economic structure and urbanization emerged as most important variables for characteristics pattern of sex ratio in the state. Sex composition constituted one of the most readily observable elements of population and was an important effect of population composition.
- **Mehta and Kaur** (1983) explained that rural-urban differentials in sex ratio in Rajasthan, were characterized by low sex ratio which was still lower in urban areas. Assuming little difference in sex ratio at birth, both in rural and urban areas, sex selectively had been found inversely related to the growth rate of urban population. Generally, urban sex ratio was lower than that of rural because of male selective flow of immigrants to urban centers.
- **Dyson and Moore** (1983) led the studies on how there exists dichotomy in the kinship structure between North and South India, which was found to determine the degree of autonomy enjoyed by women, which in turn would translate its effects on fertility and infant mortality. In contrast to states in the north, southern states were

characterized by lower marital fertility, later age at marriage, lower infant and child mortality and comparatively low ratio of female to male infant and child mortality. The hypothesis and analysis put forward in this paper is often criticized for lack of economic and district controls and is examined with latest time and again.

• **Desai and Patel (1985)** analyzed the decadal change in sex ratio, the most worst situations are in Haryana, Punjab, Rajasthan and Delhi, where there is dark age for female child. The fashionable and affluent district of Delhi has witnessed a 50 point drop in the past decade; although these states are more economically developed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Here in this section we are dealing with results and discussions with particular reference to different blocks or tahsils of Bhiwani district.

Years	Sex Ratio (Haryana)	Sex Ratio (Bhiwani)
1991	879	887
2001	819	841
2011	830	831

Table 1: Bhiwani District and Haryana: Trends in CSR (1991-2011)

Source:-Census of India (1991-2011)

Fig. 1: Bhiwani District and Haryana: Trends in Child Sex Ratio (1991-2011)

Source:-Based on Table 1

In this table the trends of child Sex Ratio from 1991 to 2011 was discussed in Haryana as well as in Bhiwani. In 1991 the Child Sex Ratio of Haryana was 879 which declines 60 points, in 2001 (819), which was a positive signal for gender balance. During the same period Bhiwani

district to had continue declining trend in 1991, 2001,2011, Bhiwani district had 887,841,831 which goes continuous decline from time to time. It was considered 84 points decline from 1991 to 2001 and 27 points from 2001 to 2011.

Source:-

Map 1: Based on Census of India (1991)

Years	Child Sex Ratio	Change
1991	887	-
2001	841	46
2011	831	10

Table 2: Bhiwani District: Child Sex Ratio (1991 to 2011)

Source: - Census of India (1991-2011)

Table 2 and map 1 Shows the trend in Child Sex Ratio of Bhiwani district from 1991 to 2011. The table shows a continuous decline in Child Sex Ratio during considered period. In 1991 CSR was 887, 2001 (841), 2011 (831). From 1991 to 2001 CSR decrease 46 points which was a large gap between boys and girls. From 2001 to 2011 it

decreases 10 points which was less than from first decade but continuous decline in CSR was a serious issue. It means sex selective abortion and son preference have spread like an epidemic in last to decade and infant mortality rate is comparatively higher for female children than male children.

Map 2

Source:-Based on Census of India (2001)

District/Tehsils	Child Sex Ratio		Decadal Change
	1991	2001	
Bhiwani	890	832	58
Dadri	891	819	72
Loharu	860	859	1
Tosham	880	868	12
Badhra	867	850	17
Bawani khera	894	883	11
Siwani Mandi	880	856	24

Table 3: Bhiwani District Decadal Decline in CSR by Tehsils (1991-2001)

Source:-Census of India (1991-2001)

Fig. 2: Bhiwani District: Decadal Decline in Child Sex-Ratio by Tehsils (1991-2001)

Source:-Based on Table 3

Table 3 and map 2 shows the decadal decline from 1991 to 2001, Tehsil wise in Bhiwani district. This table shows a continuous decline of Child Sex Ratio in all 7 Tehsils. Highest decline found in the Dadri Tehsil in this Tehsil CSR in 1991 was 891 but in 2001 it was 819, a decline of 72 points, which was highest in all Tehsils.

Second largest decline was in Bhiwani Tehsil, 52 points then Siwani Mandi 24 points, Badhra 17 points, Tosham 12 points, Bawani Khera 11 points, Loharu 1 point only. Loharu Tehsil had only decline of 1 point which is desirable change in

Tehsils	2001	2011	Change
Bhiwani	832	831	1
Dadri	819	810	9
Loharu	859	828	31
Tosham	868	856	12
Badara	850	798	52
Bawani Khera	883	852	31
Siwani Mandi	856	891	35

Table 4: Bhiwani District Tehsil Wise Decadal Change in Child Sex Ratio (2001-2011)

Source: - Census of India (2001-2011)

Fig. 3: Bhiwani District: Decadal Change in Child Sex-Ratio by Tehsils (2001-2011)

Source:-Based on Table 4

Source:-

Map 3: Based on Census of India (2011)

The current table 4 shows the decadal change in Child Sex Ratio Tehsil wise from 2001 to 2011. The data shows the positive and negative growth in some tehsils. Only one tehsil, Siwani Mandi had positive growth in CSR that is 35 points (856 in 2001 and 891 in 2011). The other tehsils

shows the decline in CSR. The highest was found in Badhra that was 52 points. Then followed by Bawani Khera 31 points, Loharu 31 points, Tosham 12 points, Dadri 9 points and Bhiwani only 1 points.

Tehsils	2001	2011	Change
Bhiwani	844	835	9
Dadri	823	812	11
Loharu	855	851	4
Tosham	865	856	9
Badhra	820	798	22
Bawani Khera	880	859	21
Siwani Mandi	859	898	39

Table 5: Bhiwani District: Decadal Comparative Analysis in Rural Areas (2001-2011)

Source: -Census of India (2001-2011)

Fig. 4: Bhiwani District : Decadal Comparative Analysis in Urban Areas (2001-2011)

Source:-Based on Table 5

Table 5 explains the decadal comparative analyses of rural areas in Bhiwani district from 2001 to 2011. From this table we come to know only one tehsil Siwani Mandi had positive growth in CSR (859 in 2001 and 898 in 2011) that is increment of 39 points. The other tehsils had negative growth in CSR. The pattern followed by these tehsil Badhra 22 points then Bawani Khera 21 points, Dadri 11 points, Tosham 9 points, Bhiwani 9 points and Loharu 4 points.

IV. CONCLUSION

The sex ratio in India improved by as much as 13 points between 1991 and 2011, however despite this, the number of girls per 1000 males in the population is still 32 points lower. The drop in sex differentials in mortality is largely responsible for the improvement in the country's overall sex ratio. Furthermore, this is primarily a problem among adults. Child sex ratio in the age group of 0-6 years have been declining at an alarming rate in recent years, which will have serious ramifications for all age sex ratios in the future, considering that several of the main states have seen a decrease of 50 points in child sex ratios. In Bhiwani district the situation of sex ratio (Both at aggregate level or juvenile stage). In rural areas highest decline is noticed in Badhra tahsil (22 points) and highest increase is noticed in Siwani Mandi (39 points) in recent decade. In context to urban areas, situation is not changed although much worried, there were 72 points declined in only Dadri tahsil during 2001-11 decade.

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